

PROJECT'S OUTCOMES

To provide new insights and knowledge in ensuring the wider and more efficient use of proteins from alternative sources. This will contribute to tackling the deficit in the EU's soybean imports

ALEHOOP will boost the innovation capacity for the companies involved while creating new market opportunities in different sectors: legume and algae processing, feed and functional food industries

To establish three new cross-sectoral interconnections in the biobased economy

ALEHOOP will reduce food wastage and thus reduce unnecessary water and energy consumption and loss of biodiversity

To create 14 new bio-based value chains: 2 in the green algae-based sector, 6 in brown algae-based sector and a further 6 in the legume by-product sector

To contribute to developing six new products in the food and beverage sector and two in the animal feed sector

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COORDINATION, EXPLOITATION & BUSINESS PLAN, LCSA

FRUITS PREPARATIONS, LEGUME SUPPLIER

PROTEINS EXTRACTION FROM BROWN SEAWEED BY-PRODUCTS AND SCALING-UP

FEEDS FOR POULTRY AND PIGS

BIOAVAILABILITY STUDIES, PROTEINS CHARACTERISATION

SMOOTHFOOD, MEAL REPLACEMENTS SHAKES, VEGGIE PRODUCTS

SCALE-UP OF PROTEINS PRODUCTIO FROM LEGUMES

PROTEINS EXTRACTION FROM GREEN SEAWEED BY PRODUCTS AND SCALING-UP

PROTEINS EXTRACTION FROM LEGUME BY PRODUCTS

REGULATORY ASPECTS

AQUAFEED

FEED PERFORMANCE IN CHICKENS & PIGS

BIOREFINERIES FOR THE VALORISATION OF MACROALGAL RESIDUAL BIOMASS AND LEGUME PROCESSING BY-PRODUCTS TO OBTAIN NEW PROTEIN VALUE CHAINS FOR HIGH-VALUE FOOD AND FEED APPLICATIONS

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 887259

CHALLENGE 2

ALEHOOP addresses 2 main challenges:

To satisfy the deficit of protein supply in Europe through alternative protein sources in a sustainable way and meeting expected requirements

1. Proteins extracted from **green seaweed** incorporated into animal feed.
2. Proteins extracted from **green seaweed** incorporated into aquafeed.
3. **Legume** and **brown seaweed by-products** as an alternative source of protein for food products.

To find an economical & sustainable management of aquatic and terrestrial residual biomass

1. **Residual biomass by seaweed processors** → brown seaweed-based biorefinery.
2. **Residual biomass in legume processing industry** → legume-based biorefinery.
3. **Aquatic biomass from algal blooms** → green seaweed-based biorefinery.

KEY VALUE PROPOSITION

ALEHOOP proteins	Animal feed containing ALEHOOP proteins	Food products containing ALEHOOP proteins
Lower carbon footprint (-30% vs current conventional protein production process)	Better digestibility of selected extracts	Enhanced nutritional profile
	Good balance between aminoacids and minerals, vitamins, etc. in selected raw materials	Enhanced techno-functional properties
Low-price feedstock (-25%) that is available in large quantities: durable protein supply	Pairing different materials will help compensate the unbalanced aminoacid profile of one type of plant-based protein	Affordable and healthy
	Replacement of part of imported soy	Animal-free protein foods suitable for specific population groups, such as celiac people
	Lower Exworks price (-5%)	

THE CONCEPT

The Alehoop project provides the demonstration at pilot scale of both sustainable macroalgae (commonly known as seaweed) and legume-based biorefineries for the recovery of low-cost dietary proteins from alga-based and plant residual biomass and their validation to meet market requirements of consumers and industry in the food and feed sectors

Proteins and amino acids are the building blocks of life, playing a critical biological role in living organisms due to their nutritional and physiological properties. In addition to their biofunctionality, proteins also play important roles in foods affecting their appearance, texture and stability because of technofunctional properties such as solubility, viscosity, foaming, emulsification and gelation properties

FINAL PRODUCTS

LEGEND

